

Evolution of Fine Structure Constant

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the fine structure constant is calculated by considering volume of 4-dimensional space time sphere. Furthermore, the value of fine structure constant at energy scale of W boson is calculated by using calculated value of fine structure constant.

Keywords: Fine structure constant, volume of sphere, fine structure constant at high energy

Explanation of Theoretical Formula

The simple formula for fine structure constant can be expressed as

$$\frac{1}{\alpha} = \frac{\frac{4}{3}\pi\left(\frac{4}{3}\pi\right)^3\left(\frac{4}{3}\right)^3}{4\pi^{1/4}\beta_0} \quad (1)$$

The numerator term in right hand side of the Eq. (1) can be considered as volume of sphere.

In the Rutherford-Bohr atomic model of the hydrogen atom, let's assume the radius for n=3

orbit is $\left(\frac{4}{3}\pi\right)^3$ and radius of n=2 orbit is $\left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^3$. The ratio of these two radiuses creates vertex

for the electron-positron interaction to produce photon in the Feynman diagram. The

denominator term in right hand side of the Eq. (1) is the multiple of 4-dimensional isotropic volume element but with surface Q^1 [1] and $\beta_0 = \sqrt{1 - (\alpha_0)^2}$ [2].

The simple expression for $\frac{1}{\alpha_0}$ to calculate β_0 can be written as

$$\frac{1}{\alpha_0} = \frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{4}{3} \pi \right)^3 \times \frac{2 \times 3 \times 5 \times 7}{32 \times 2\sqrt{2} \times 3\sqrt{3}} \quad (2)$$

In the above Eq. (2), volume of sphere multiplied by multiples of single digit prime numbers. We can also explain multiples of prime numbers by a simple theory: an electron and a positron (i.e. 2) produce photon (i.e. 3) that becomes a quark and anti-quark pair (i.e. 5) and after which anti-quark radiates a gluon. These gluons bind quarks together to form hadrons [3] (i.e. 7). This phenomenon can also be seen in the Feynman diagram. 32 is the number of different quarks survives at zero entropy [4] or 32 (i.e. 2^5) represents the 5-dimensional group $O(4,1)$. $2\sqrt{2}$ is the two mass-less particle in singlet state and $3\sqrt{3}$ is the 3 colour for each flavour with line joining at finite distance [5] or $2\sqrt{2}$ and $3\sqrt{3}$ represents the Eight-order Feynman diagram on electron self-interaction.

Now, multiply right hand side of Eq. (2) by complex light cone number (i.e. $\frac{7}{3 \times 3^{1/4} \times \sqrt{\pi}}$).

The numerator term in this number come from the symmetric group of degree 7 or particles interaction in the Feynman diagram (discussed above) and the denominator term in this number come from multiples of 4-dimensional cone whose cross sections form 3D sphere and Gaussian integral. Thus, the expression for $\frac{1}{\alpha_0}$ can be rewritten as

$$\frac{1}{\alpha_0} = \frac{4}{3} \pi \left(\frac{4}{3} \pi \right)^3 \times \frac{5}{2 \times 3} \times \left(\frac{7}{4} \right)^2 \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{2} \times \sqrt{3} \times \sqrt{\pi} \times 3^{1/4}} \quad (3)$$

The Eq. (3) is the multiples of volume of sphere and universal gravitation law or Coulomb law of electrostatic force.

Calculation of Dimensionless Fine Structure Constants

I. After inserting Eq. (2) in Eq. (1), the fine structure constant value will come

$$\frac{1}{\alpha} = 137.03600756538... \quad (4)$$

Where, $\beta_0 = 0.999973540478022...$

After inserting Eq. (3) in Eq. (1), the exact theoretical value of fine structure constant will come

$$\frac{1}{\alpha} = 137.03599727639... \quad (5)$$

Where, $\beta_0 = 0.9999735528322...$

The calculated value of fine structure constant in Eq. (5) is equal to the value reported in the references [6] round to 7 decimal places.

II. The fine structure constant at high energy $\left(\frac{1}{\alpha_h}\right)$ can be expressed as

$$\frac{1}{\alpha_h} = \frac{27 \times 3\sqrt{3}}{16 \times 3\pi \times \alpha} = 127.49384987327... \quad (6)$$

In the above Eq. (6), 3 lines coincides the vertex in the Feynman diagram resulting 3π . The fine structure constant value is taken from Eq. (5) in the above Eq. (6). The calculated value of fine structure constant at high energy in Eq. (6) is approximately equal to the value reported in the reference [7].

Acknowledgements: During this COVID-19 time, I was supported by personal savings and by Shri Niranjan Dev Sannyasa Aashram, Ram Ghat, North Coast, Village Lutgaon, Dindori 481880, INDIA. Very special thanks go to Kaamdhenu Gaushala Samiti, Ram Ghat, North Coast, Village Lutgaon, Dindori 481880, INDIA for giving me the great opportunity to do this work at the bank of Holy River Narmada. I did this work by the grace of Swami Ram Sharan Puri, Dr. Abhinav Shukla, Mangala Shukla and Ramakant Shukla. I'd like to thank particularly to Prof. Rakesh Bajpai, Prof. Yao Zhen, Dr. Sambhu Bhadra and Rahul Agrawal for many valuable discussions and suggestions.

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